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Research Article

**FOLK MEDICINAL CLAIMS OF JAUNSARI TRIBE IN
SYNERGY WITH AYURVEDA**Avnish K. Upadhyay*¹ and Kaushal Kumar²¹Department of Oriental Studies, Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar-249411
(Uttarakhand)² Department of Forest Products & Utilization, Faculty of Forestry, Birsa Agriculture University,
Kanke, Ranchi-834008 (Jharkhand)**Abstract:**

This paper is an outcome of extensive study among the Jaunsari tribes and is an attempt to enlist various plant-lore and their folk claims. It has been established that Ayurveda is the most ancient medical systems of the world, evident with authoritative documents of Rigveda dealing about the origin and significance of medicinal plants for mankind. Ayurveda is a comprehensive indigenous scientific medicinal system. Continuous research on safety, quality and efficacy of Ayurvedic drugs, procedures as well as widely used folk medicines, is needed. Systematic documentation and critical analysis of clinical practice are necessary. Folk Medicine is widely used form of alternative medical practices among tribes of India including Jaunsari tribes. The data presented in the present communication delineated with botanical name, family, uses etc. The research work towards enumeration of plants is based on earlier published data along with documentations and communication under present studies. Also the synergy establishment with Ayurvedic uses has been done on the basis of extensive review of renowned classical text of Ayurveda on pharmacognosy and pharmacology. Scientific name of the plants along with their vernacular names and medicinal uses used by the tribal people and their correlation with Ayurvedic properties along with references in the study area are presented. The Jaunsari tribal people use more than hundreds of plant species belonging to 57 families for curing different ailments as described in classical Ayurvedic texts.

Keywords: Oriental Medicine, Folk-lore, Folk Medicine, Ethno-botany, Ayurveda, Jaunsari Tribe*** Corresponding Author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

It has been established that *Ayurveda* is the most ancient medical systems of the world, evident with authoritative documents of *Rigveda* dealing about the origin and significance of medicinal plants for mankind. *Ayurveda* is a comprehensive indigenous scientific medicinal system. The term *Ayurveda* means 'knowledge of life', this comprises two Sanskrit words, *Ayu* (life) and *Veda* (knowledge or science). Four *Vedas*, considered as the oldest Indian literature of 5000-1000 BC. [1] [2] *Charaka Samhita* (special emphasis on internal medicine) and *Susruta Samhita* (special emphasis on surgery) were written systematically and considered as classical text of *Ayurveda*. Vital details of *Charaka Samhita* and *Susruta Samhita* were compiled together and updated additionally in *Astanga Sangraha* and *Astanga Hridaya*. Some other ancient classics which include minor work of *Ayurveda* include *Madhava Nidana* (special emphasis on diagnosis of disease), *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu* (special emphasis on additional medicinal plants), and *Sarngadhara Samhita* (formulation and dosage form). [3]

There is a need for extensive scientific evaluation in *Ayurveda*, which has been recognized for a long time. *Ayurveda* has personalized approach involving constitutional assessment, which can guide primary prevention, diagnosis and therapeutics. *Ayurveda* also offers detailed guidance about food, nutrition and diet as per the individual constitution or *Prakriti* as well as *Ritu* or seasons. [4] The scientific value of basic principles of *Ayurveda* like *Prakriti* is being studied in context to biology and genomics. [5] *Ayurveda* as an ancient science of life has a long history, and its basic principles may be valid even today. However, essence of any science is a continuous quest for new knowledge through research, development and newer applications. Continuous research on safety, quality and efficacy of *Ayurvedic* drugs, procedures as well as widely used folk medicines, is needed. Systematic documentation and critical analysis of clinical practice are necessary.

Folk Medicine is widely used form of alternative medical practices among tribes of India including *Jaunsari Tribes*. [6] The Folk-medicine particularly as ethnomedicinal plants used by Jaunsari tribe in Jaunsar-Bhawar region has great medicinal plant-lore. [7] [8] There are hundreds of plant species used as medicine for the treatment of various diseases and disorders by the tribal community. *Ayurveda* and Folk Medicine exists side-by-side in various communities. A number of medicinal plant-lore was identified from Jaunsari tribe for their synergy establishment with *Ayurvedic* uses and indications. A

total number of 101 plants were identified from them; most of the plants used by the tribes also had similar *Ayurvedic* uses, indicating at least some *Ayurvedic* influences.

This paper is an outcome of extensive study among the *Jaunsari Tribes* and is an attempt to enlist various plant-lore and their folk claims.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

The present work has been carried out on the folk-lore or ethno-medicine of *Jaunsari Tribe* inhabitants' in the Uttarakhand state of India particularly in the district of Dehradun. The region is under the Shivalik and Himalayan mountainous chain. The data presented in the present communication delineated with botanical name, family, uses etc. The research work towards enumeration of plants is based on earlier published data along with documentations and communication under present studies. Also the synergy establishment with *Ayurvedic* uses has been done on the basis of extensive review of renowned classical text of *Ayurveda* on pharmacognosy and pharmacology related to Dravyaguna like *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu*, *Raj Nighantu*, *Kaiyadev Nighantu*, *Dhanvantari Nighantu*, *Susruta Samhita*, *Charaka Samhita*, *Shaligram Nighantu*, *Shodhala Nighantu*, *Ark Prakasha* etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The Folk-medicine particularly as ethnomedicinal plants used by Jaunsari tribe in Jaunsar-Bhawar region has great medicinal plant-lore. There are more than 100 plant species used as medicine for the treatment of various diseases and disorders by the tribal community out of which maximum folk wisdom of medicinal uses resembles with medicinal and pharmacological properties described in authentic classical texts of *Ayurveda* [Table 1]. Scientific name of the plants along with their vernacular names and medicinal uses used by the tribal people and their correlation with *Ayurvedic* properties along with references in the study area are presented. *Ayurvedic* terms of diseases/ actions and their correlates in Modern Medicine [Table 2] along with abbreviations of *Ayurvedic* Texts [Table 3] is also described and tabulated. The *Jaunsari Tribes* use a total of 101 plant species belonging to 57 families for curing different ailments as described in classical *Ayurvedic* texts. There are a large number of scientific studies are being carried out by various scholars on folk-lore and ethno-medicinal status of various communities including Jaunsari tribes. [9] [10]

Table 1: Listing of Folk Medicinal Claims in synergy with *Ayurvedic* Texts [11-24]

Botanical Name	Family	Local Name	Folk Medicinal Claims	Sanskrit Name	Validation in <i>Ayurveda</i>	<i>Ayurvedic</i> Text Reference
<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Fabaceae	Ratti, Laldana, Chuntli	Fever, Asthma, Chest Pain, Stomachache, Disorders of Nervous System, Joints Pain and Paralysis	<i>Gunja</i>	<i>Jwara, Shwaas, Shoola, Rasayana, Bhrama, Balakaraka</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 109-111</i>
<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Malvaceae	Kanghe	Fever, Dysuria	<i>Atibala</i>	<i>Mootrala, Shotha, Shoola</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 125-126</i>
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Chirchita	Bodyache and Cramps, Used as Datun in Pyorrhoea, Piles	<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Arsha, Kandu, Grahi</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Shatavhadi Varga: 91</i>
<i>Achyranthes bidentata</i> Blume	Amaranthaceae	Hwang, Golda	Toothache, Snake Bite, Wounds	<i>Apamargi, Giri-Apamarga</i>	<i>Shoola, Kandu, Chedana</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 1032-1034</i>
<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i> Wall ex Royle	Ranunculaceae	Atish	Stomachache, Fever, Cough, Diarrhea, Vomiting	<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Deepana, Paachana, Sangrahani, Sarva-doshahara</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 25</i>
<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.	Araceae	Bach	Antihelminthic, Indigestion, Cough, Dysentery, Snake Bite, Asthma.	<i>Uragandha</i>	<i>Jantujita, Paachana, Kaas</i>	<i>Dh. Ni. Shatpushpadi Varga: 7-9</i>
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees Syn <i>Adhatoda zeylanica</i> Med.	Acanthaceae	Basinga, Bhansoi	Cough, Dermatitis, Fever.	<i>Vaasa</i>	<i>Kaas, Jwara</i>	<i>Su. Su. 46</i>
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Rutaceae	Bel	Dysentery, Diarrhea, Fever	<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Atisaara, Pravahika, Grahani, Jwara</i>	<i>Su. Su. 46</i>
<i>Albizia procera</i> (Roxb.) Benth	Mimosaceae	Safed Siris, Karha, Sirsoi	Abdominal Pain, Vomiting	<i>Shwet Shirish</i>	<i>Tridosh-shamaka</i>	<i>Dh. Ni. Aamradi Varga: 113-114</i>
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br ex DC. Syn. <i>A. nudiflora</i> R.Br.	Amaranthaceae	Satarmasa	Wound Healing, Dermal Problems	<i>Matsyakshi</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Parpatadi Varga: 127</i>
<i>Amaranthus blitum</i> L. Syn. <i>A. lividus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Dant ki Jad	Toothache	<i>Shwet Maarish</i>	<i>Kshara</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 635</i>
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Amaranthaceae	Koda chaulai; Jungli chaulai	Stomachache	<i>Tanduliya</i>	<i>Udarshoola</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Mulakadi Varga: 145</i>
<i>Angelica glauca</i> Engew.	Apiaceae	Choru	Flatulence, Colic	<i>Choraka</i>	<i>Aadhmaan, Udarshoola</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 4/48</i>
<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Papaveraceae	Kandra	Leprosy	<i>Swarnakshiri</i>	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Harityakadi Varga: 155-156</i>
<i>Asparagus adscendens</i> Roxeb.	Asperagaceae	Jhirni, Kairu	Sexual Debility, Diabetes, Urinary Troubles	<i>Balyakanda</i>	<i>Vrshya, Rasayana</i>	<i>Ma. Ni. Abhayadi Varga: 269</i>

<i>Asparagus filicinus</i> Buch. -Ham ex D. Don	Asperagaceae	Kaunta	Aphrodisiac	<i>Viral Kand Satavar</i>	<i>Vrshya, Rasayana</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 160</i>
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd; <i>Asparagus curillus</i> Buch. -Ham ex Roxb.	Asperagaceae	Sharanoi, Bekui, Satarwal, Satawar	Dysentery, Acne, Milk Yield	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Atisaara, Stanya</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 1063-1064</i>
<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	Acanthaceae	Kala bansa	Cough, Wound Healing, Inflammation	<i>Saireyak</i>	<i>Kaphaghna, Vrana, Shotha</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Pushpavarga: 53</i>
<i>Berberis aristata</i> DC; <i>Berberis lycium</i> Royle	Berberidaceae	Kashmoi	Ophthalmic Problems	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Netrya</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Harityakadi Varga: 177</i>
<i>Bergenia ciliata</i> (Haw.) Sternb. Syn. <i>Saxifera ligulata</i> Wall.	Saxifragaceae	Dhaklabu, Silpara, Dhonk, Phulute, Shilphora, Pattarchoor	Renal Calculus, Sores, Inflammation	<i>Pashanbheda</i>	<i>Ashmarihara</i>	<i>Dha. Ni. Guduchyadi Varga: 209</i>
<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i> L.	Nyctaginaceae	Phurnoi, Punarnava, Purnoi, Jangli sabji	Jaundice, Asthma, Bronchitis, Eye Problems, Inflammation	<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Shotha, Pandu, Shwaas, Kaas, Netrya</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Parpatadi Varga: 116</i>
<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L. Syn. <i>B. malabaricum</i> DC	Malvaceae	Semal	Boils, Neurological Disorders	<i>Shalmali</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Vatadi Varga: 45-46</i>
<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub. Syn. <i>B. frondosa</i> Roxb.	Fabaceae	Dhak, Palas	Ulcers, Sore Throat, Diarrhea, Dysentery, Haemorrhage in Stomach and Bladder	<i>Palash</i>	<i>Vrana, Kaphahara, Atisaara, Sangrahani, Gulma</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Vatadi Varga: 40-44</i>
<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i> Vahl.	Verbenaceae	Daiya	Rheumatoid Arthritis	<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Aamvata</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 85-86</i>
<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br. & <i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Ait.	Apocynaceae	Aank	Boils, Expectorant, Cold, Cough, Asthma	<i>Arka</i>	<i>Vrana, Shopha, Kaphahara</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Karviradi Varga: 28-32</i>
<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Cannabaceae	Bhang	Hydrocele	<i>Bhanga</i>	<i>Vrishan Shotha</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. III: 1116</i>
<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Fabaceae	Ban Lakdi, Amaltash, Kirala, Sinara, Kindawa	Constipation, Stomachache, Urinary Disorders	<i>Aaragvadha</i>	<i>Koshth-shuddhi</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Harityakadi Varga: 133</i>
<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> (L.) Rose	Caesalpiniaceae	Chakunda	Skin Disorders, Wounds	<i>Kasmard</i>	<i>Twakroga, Vrana</i>	<i>D.G.V. : 2/288</i>
<i>Cassia tora</i> L.	Caesalpiniaceae	Chakvad	Skin Disorders, Hemorrhoids, Snake Bite	<i>Chakramarda</i>	<i>Kushtha, Vibandha</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Harityakadi Varga: 183-185</i>
<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb.) Loud.	Pinaceae	Deodar	Cough, Piles, Itching	<i>Devdaru</i>	<i>Kandu, Vibandha, Kaas</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 23-24</i>

<i>Celastrus paniculata</i> Willd.	Celastraceae	Malkangni, Malkani, Athnoi, Papkakni	Boils	<i>Jyotishmati</i>	<i>Daha</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Guduchyadi Varga</i> : 82-83
<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urban	Apiaceae	Brahmi	Brain Tonic, Dermatitis, Blood Purification, Diuretic	<i>Brahmi, Mandukparni</i>	<i>Medhya, Rasayana</i>	Ch. Chi. 1.3: 30, 31
<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> Nees & Eberm.	Lauraceae	Tej Patta, Gurandra	Cold, Rheumatism, Diarrhea	<i>Tejpatra, Tamalpatra</i>	<i>Kaphaghn, Vatahara, Atisaara</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Pipaliyadi Varga</i> : 175
<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Menispermaceae	Parh	Diabetes, Bone Fracture	<i>Paatha</i>	<i>Tikta, Bhagna-sandhan</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Pipaliyadi Varga</i> : 121
<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Cleomaceae	Jungli Mithi, Mithi	Asthma	<i>Tilparni, Hurhur</i>	<i>Shwaas</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Shatavhadi Varga</i> : 177-178
<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt Syn. <i>C. indica</i> Wight & Arn.	Cucurbitaceae	Kanduri	Snake Bite	<i>Bimbi, Tundicari</i>	<i>Sarpadansha</i>	Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. II: 1062
<i>Crotalaria prostrata</i> Rottl. ex Willd.	Fabaceae	Chunchui	Dysentery	<i>Shana</i>	<i>Grahi</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Shatavhadi Varga</i> : 76
<i>Curcuma domestica</i> (Medik) Valh Syn <i>C. longa</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kachchi haldi	Abdominal Pain, Internal Wounds	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Shoola, Deha Vrana</i>	Dha. Ni. <i>Guduchyadi Varga</i> : 57-60
<i>Curcuma zedoaria</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Kachoor	Stomachache	<i>Karchoor, Kalpak</i>	<i>Deepana, Paachana</i>	Dh. Ni. <i>Chandanadi Varga</i> : 102
<i>Cuscuta europaea</i> Bove & Engelm.	Cuscutaceae	Akash-laguli	Skin Disease	<i>Amarvalli</i>	<i>Kandu</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Guduchyadi Varga</i> : 55
<i>Cyathula tomentosa</i> Miq. Syn. <i>Achyranthes tomentosa</i> Roth	Amaranthaceae	Sirli	Boils	<i>Raktapamarg</i>	<i>Chhedana</i>	Kai. Ni. <i>Aushadhi Varga</i> : 1033-34
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	Doob, Dubla	Dysentery, Fever	<i>Durva, Neeldurva</i>	<i>Daha, Aamatisaara</i>	Bha. Ni., <i>Guduchyadi Varga</i> : 149-150
<i>Dactylorrhiza hatagirea</i> (D. Don) Soo Syn. <i>Orchis latifolia</i> Auct. non L.	Orchidaceae	Salam Panja, Salam Misri, Sakloi	Nose Bleed	<i>Munjatak</i>	<i>Snigdha</i>	Ch. Su. 27
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L. Syn <i>Datura sauveolens</i> H&B.	Solanaceae	Safed Dhatura	Facial Skin Problems, Ear-ache, Asthma	<i>Dhattur</i>	<i>Varnya</i>	Bha. Ni., <i>Guduchyadi Varga</i> : 75-76
<i>Delphinium denudatum</i> Wall. ex Hook. f & Thoms.	Ranunculaceae	Nirvishi, Judwar	Toothache, Snake-Bite, Cough	<i>Nirvisha</i>	<i>Dantshoola, Updansha, Kaas</i>	Ra. Ni. <i>Pippalayadi Varga</i> : 218-219
<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Dioscoreaceae	Gainthi	Bronchitis, Antiseptic, Burn, Wound	<i>Varahikanda</i>	<i>Shleshmaghn, Rasayana, Vrana</i>	Su. Su. 46: 309
<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Gaertn.	Euphorbiaceae	Amla	Stomach Diseases, Hair Tonic	<i>Aamalaki</i>	<i>Sarv-doshkhara</i>	Su. Su. 46: 143-144
<i>Ephedra gerardiana</i> Wallich ex C.A. Meyer	Ephedraceae	Tutgantha	Low Blood Pressure, Arthritis	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Shohta, Shoola</i>	D.G.V. 2/303-304

<i>Eupatorium adenophorum</i> Spreng	Asteraceae	Kharna/ Bakura	Wounds	Aayapan	Vrana	D.G.V. 2/789-790
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Dudhibari	Hemorrhoids, Bronchitis, Asthma	Dugdhika	Raktarsha, Fuffush-shohta, Shwaas	Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. – 767
<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> L.	Convolvulaceae	Sankhpushpi	Cough, Cold, Asthma, Bronchitis	Nilpushpa	Shwaas, Jwara	Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. - 1453-1454
<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Peepal	Burn	Pippal	Dagdha Vrana/ Daha	Ra. Ni. Aamradi Varga: 114-115
<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Liliaceae	Langlya	Painful Delivery, Difficulty in Urination	Kalihari, Langali	Sukhprasava	Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 71-72
<i>Hedychium spicatum</i> Buch. Ham.	Zingiberaceae	Kapoorkachri/ Banhaldi/ Kachoor	Dyspepsia, Asthma, Arthritis, Inflammation, Wounds	Shati, Gandhmulika	Shohta, Kaas, Shwaas, Vrana, Shoola	Bha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 83
<i>Juglans regia</i> L.	Juglandaceae	Akhor, Akhrot	Tooth Brush	Akshot	Rochana	Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 375-376
<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> (Roth.) Spreng.	Lamiaceae	Dronpushpi	Diaphoretic, Snake Bite, Worms	Drona	Jantujita	Arka Prakash Tritiy Shatak: 92
<i>Litsea glutinosa</i> (Lour.) Robins	Lauraceae	Maida-lakri	Bone Fracture, Wound	Medasak	Asthibhagna	D.G.V. 2/78-79
<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Muell.-Arg.	Euphorbiaceae	Kamil, Kamlu	Itching, Abdominal Pain	Kampillak	Aanaaha, Vishaghna	Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 949-950
<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Meliaceae	Bakain	Dermatitis, Rheumatic Pain, Worms	Mahanimb	Kushtha, Gulma, Raktvikara	Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 86
<i>Mentha arvensis</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Pudeena	Dysentery	Putiha	Sangrahani	Sha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 71
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam. syn. <i>M. pterygosperma</i> Gaertn.	Moringaceae	Sondhi, Sondi	Scorpion Bite, Snake Bite	Shigru	Vishanashanam	Bha. Ni., Guduchyadi Varga: 96
<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Spreng.	Rutaceae	Gandheli	Antihelminthic	Surabhinimb	Krimi	Ra. Ni., Prabhadradi Varga: 11-14
<i>Myrica esculenta</i> Buch.-Ham	Myricaceae	Kaphal	Headache	Katphal	Shoola	Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 160
<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> DC.	Valerianaceae	Jatamasi	Epilepsy, Hysteria	Bhootjata	Aakshepaka, Apasmara	Ra. Ni. Chandanadi Varga: 96-97
<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Tobacco	Scabies	Tamraparna	Krimi	Sha. Ni. Parishisht Bhag: 908
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Tulsi	Fever, Cough	Sulabha	Kaphahara	Dh. Ni. Karviradi Gana: 50
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Bantulsi	Bronchitis, Cough, Diarrhea, Abdominal Pain	Maruvak	Kaphahara	Bha. Ni. Pushpa Varga: 53

<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Oxalidaceae	Salmudi, khatti-mithi, Bhilmori	Abdominal Pain, Fever, Vomiting, Cataract, Conjunctivitis	<i>Chaangeri</i>	<i>Deepana, Sangrahani, Netrya</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Mulakadi Varga: 148</i>
<i>Papaver somniferum</i> L.	Papaveraceae	Post	Bodyache	<i>Ahifen</i>	<i>Ushna, Shoola</i>	<i>D.G.V. 2/23</i>
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> Sarg.	Pinaceae	Chir	Sprain	<i>Surabhidaruk</i>	<i>Snigdoshna (Muscle Relaxing Properties)</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 25</i>
<i>Pistacia integerrima</i> J.L. Swewart ex Brandis	Anacardiaceae	Kalera, Kakroi, Kakrasringi	Asthma, Cough, Fever	<i>Karkatshringi</i>	<i>Kaas, Shwaas, Jwara</i>	<i>Dh. Ni. Guduchyadi Varga: 96-97</i>
<i>Plantago depressa</i> Willd.	Plantaginaceae	Luhurya/Isabgol	Wounds, Piles, Abdominal Problems	<i>Ashwagol</i>	<i>Raktatisara</i>	<i>Sha. Ni. Parishisht Bhag: 909-910</i>
<i>Prunus armeniaca</i> L.	Rosaceae	Chula, Khubani	Headache	<i>Uruman</i>	<i>Vatashamak</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra I. 182-183</i>
<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> D. Don	Rosaceae	Panya	Psychological Disorders, Inflammation	<i>Padmaka</i>	<i>Moha (Delusion)</i>	<i>Dha. Ni. Chandanadi Varga: 96</i>
<i>Prunus persica</i> Batsch	Rosaceae	Aadu	Acne	<i>Aaruk</i>	<i>Twakroga</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Aamradi Varga: 99</i>
<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	Punicaceae	Darim, Damoi, Anar	Abdominal Distension, Cough, Fever	<i>Dadim</i>	<i>Gulma, Jwara</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Aamradi Varga: 86</i>
<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i> (L) Benth. ex Kurz	Apocynaceae	Sarpghandha	Fever, Anxiety, Epilepsy, Abdominal Disorders	<i>Dhawalvitapa</i>	<i>Shoola, Jwara, Apasmara, Bhrama</i>	<i>D.G.V.: 2/39</i>
<i>Rhododendron arboretum</i> Sm.	Ericaceae	Burans	Dysentery	<i>Himbaransh</i>	<i>Atisaara, Pravahika</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. 1069</i>
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Indaru, Khanash	Pain, Inflammation, Bodyache	<i>Erand</i>	<i>Vatashamak</i>	<i>Su. Su. 45: 114</i>
<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Charchora	Snake-Bite, Boils, Blisters	<i>Manjishtha</i>	<i>Vrana, Vishaghna</i>	<i>Dha. Ni. Guduchyadi Varga: 18-19</i>
<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L.	Poaceae	Kushka, Kusha	Septic Conditions	<i>Kaas</i>	<i>Lekhana</i>	<i>Ra. Ni. Shalmalyadi Varga: 88-89</i>
<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> Gaertn.	Sapindaceae	Reethachilka	Hair Tonic	<i>Arishtak</i>	<i>Keshya</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. 1268</i>
<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	Smilacaceae	Kukardara	Diuretic, Rheumatoid Arthritis	<i>Chopchini</i>	<i>Mootrala, Vatvyadhi</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 97</i>
<i>Solanum ferox</i> L.	Solanaceae	Bhut-kataia	Vomiting	<i>Kantkari</i>	<i>Chhardi</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. I: 218</i>
<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Solanaceae	Khalarkoi, Bhomolan, Makoi	Fever, Skin Disease, Acne, Diarrhea, Eye Ailments, Piles	<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Jwara, Twakroga, Atisaara, Netrya, Arsha</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Guduchyadi Varga: 247</i>
<i>Spondias pinnata</i> (L.f.) Kerz	Anacardiaceae	Amra	Ear-ache, Abdominal Discomfort	<i>Aamrataka</i>	<i>Karna Shoola, Udarroga</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. I: 73</i>

<i>Swertia angustifolia</i> Buch.-Ham. ex D.Don	Gentianaceae	Chirotu	Blood Disease, Malaria	<i>Kirataiktika</i>	<i>Sannipat Jwara</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 137</i>
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Jamun	Diabetes	<i>Jambu</i>	<i>Grahi</i>	<i>Ch. Su. 27:140</i>
<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.	Taxaceae	Thuner	Asthma, Boil, Headache	<i>Shukapushpa</i>	<i>Jwara, Jantujita</i>	<i>Bha. Ni. Karpuradi Varga: 94</i>
<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> Roxb.	Combretaceae	Baheda	Edema, Abdominal Disorders	<i>Vibhitaka</i>	<i>Kapha- Vatahara</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 35</i>
<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Combretaceae	Hera	Abdominal Disorders, Cold, Cough	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Kaas, Grahani, Vivandha</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 18-24</i>
<i>Thalictrum foliolosum</i> DC.	Ranunculaceae	Mamiri	Ophthalmic Inflammation, Fever, Stomachache	<i>Pitranga</i>	<i>Netrya</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra.II: 958</i>
<i>Tinospora sinensis</i> (Lour.) Merrill	Menispermaceae	Giloy	Debility, Leprosy, Urinary Disorders, Malaria	<i>Amrita, Madhuparni</i>	<i>Vayah- Sthapana Jwara</i>	<i>Sho. Ni. Guduchyadi Varga: 96</i>
<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i> (L.) Sprague	Apiaceae	Ajwain	Cold, Abdominal Pain	<i>Ajmodika, Yavani</i>	<i>Aanaaha, Kaphahara</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Harityakadi Varga: 75-76</i>
<i>Valeriana jatamansi</i> Jones	Valerianaceae	Samewa, Khamuri	Aphrodisiac, Mental Disorders, Tooth Problems	<i>Tagar</i>	<i>Apasmara, Shoola, Vishaadhna</i>	<i>Bha. Ni., Karpuradi Varga: 26-27</i>
<i>Viola betonicifolia</i> J. E. Sm. Var. <i>napaulensis</i> (Ging.) Bech.	Violaceae	Banafsa	Sinusitis, Skin Disorders, Fever, Cough	<i>Vanapsa</i>	<i>Jwara, Kaas, Twakroga</i>	<i>D.G.V.: 2/270</i>
<i>Vitex nigundo</i> L.	Verbenaceae	Sinwali	Rheumatoid Arthritis, Antihelminthic	<i>Nirgundi</i>	<i>Shoola, Shotha, Krimi</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 127-130</i>
<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal	Solanaceae	Ashwagandh	Urinary Disorders, Fever, Insomnia	<i>Varahkarni</i>	<i>Rasayana</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 1046</i>
<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (L.) Kertz	Lythraceae	Dhuala	Hemorrhoids, Vaginitis	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Garbha- sthanan</i>	<i>Dh. Ni. Chandanadi Varga: 98</i>
<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i> DC.	Rutaceae	Timru, Timbur	Toothache, Tooth decay	<i>Tumbaru, Tejovati</i>	<i>Dantroga</i>	<i>Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra. II:725</i>
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Adrak	Dysentery, Bronchitis	<i>Naagar, Aardrak</i>	<i>Deepana, Paachana, Kantha- vishodhan</i>	<i>Kai. Ni. Aushadhi Varga: 1160- 1162</i>

Table 2: Ayurvedic terms of diseases/ actions and their correlates in Modern Medicine

Ayurvedic Terms	Correlates in Modern Medicine	Ayurvedic Terms	Correlates in Modern Medicine
<i>Aadhmaan</i>	Flatulence, Tympanitis	<i>Mootrala</i>	Diuretic
<i>Aakshepaka</i>	Convulsions	<i>Mutraroga</i>	Renal Disorders
<i>Aamatisaara, Atisaara</i>	Diarrhea	<i>Netra Roga</i>	Ophthalmic Disorders
<i>Aamvata</i>	Rheumatoid Arthritis	<i>Netrya</i>	Eye Tonic
<i>Aanaaha</i>	Constipation	<i>Paachana</i>	Digestive Tonic
<i>Apasmara</i>	Epilepsy	<i>Pandu</i>	Anemia
<i>Arsha</i>	Piles	<i>Pravahika</i>	Frequent Loose Motions
<i>Ashmarihara</i>	Renal Calculus	<i>Raktarsha</i>	Piles with Blood
<i>Asthibhagna</i>	Bone Fracture	<i>Raktatisara</i>	Diarrhea with Blood
<i>Balakaraka</i>	Energetic, Strengthening Agents	<i>Raktvikara</i>	Blood Disorders
<i>Bhagna-sandhan</i>	Fracture	<i>Rasayana</i>	Rejuvenating Tonic
<i>Bhrama</i>	Hypochondriasis, Vertigo	<i>Rochana</i>	Appetizer
<i>Charmaroga</i>	Dermatitis	<i>Rukshoola</i>	Abdominal Pain
<i>Chhardi</i>	Vomiting	<i>Sangrahani</i>	Dysentery, IBS
<i>Chhedana</i>	Expectorant, Excision	<i>Sannipataj Jwara</i>	Chronic Fever
<i>Dadru</i>	Ring Worm	<i>Sarpadansha</i>	Anti-venom
<i>Dagdh</i>	Burn	<i>Sarv-doshhara</i>	Immune Booster
<i>Daha</i>	Burning Sensation	<i>Shleshmaghna</i>	Antitussive
<i>Dantroga</i>	Dental Problems	<i>Shoola</i>	Pain
<i>Dantshoola</i>	Toothache	<i>Shopha</i>	Edema
<i>Datun</i>	Natural Dental Brush	<i>Shotha</i>	Inflammation
<i>Deepana</i>	Enzyme Activity Enhancement	<i>Shukravruddhi</i>	Aphrodisiac
<i>Fuffushshotha</i>	Lung Inflammation	<i>Shwaas</i>	Asthma
<i>Garbha-sthapan</i>	Conception	<i>Snehakarma</i>	Lubricant
<i>Grahani</i>	IBS (Irritable Bowel Syndrome)	<i>Stanya</i>	Enhances Breast Milk Production
<i>Grahi</i>	Astringents	<i>Sukhprasava</i>	Normal Delivery
<i>Gulma</i>	Abdominal Tumor/ Distension	<i>Tikta</i>	Bitter
<i>Jantujita</i>	Antihelminthic	<i>Twakroga</i>	Skin Disease
<i>Jwara</i>	Pyrexia, Fever	<i>Udararoga</i>	Peptic Disorders
<i>Kaas</i>	Cough	<i>Udarashoola</i>	Abdominal Pain
<i>Kandu</i>	Itching	<i>Updansha</i>	Syphilis
<i>Kantha-vishodhan</i>	Mouth Freshener	<i>Ushna</i>	Hot Properties
<i>Karnashoola</i>	Earache	<i>Varnya</i>	Complexion Promoter
<i>Keshya</i>	Hair Tonic	<i>Vibandha</i>	Constipation
<i>Koshth-shuddhi</i>	Constipation	<i>Vishaghna</i>	Anti-dote
<i>Krimi</i>	Antihelminthic	<i>Vrana</i>	Wound
<i>Kushtha</i>	Leprosy, Dermatitis	<i>Vrihana</i>	Weight Enhancer
<i>Mastiskroga</i>	Nervous Disorders	<i>Vrishan Shotha</i>	Testicular Inflammation
<i>Medhya</i>	Brain Tonic	<i>Vrshya</i>	Aphrodisiac

Table 3: Abbreviations of Ayurvedic Texts

Bha. Ni.	<i>Bhavprakash Nighantu</i>	Ayurved Ja. Bu. Ra.	<i>Ayurved Jadi Buti Rahasya</i>
Ra. Ni.	<i>Raj Nighantu</i>	D.G.V.	<i>Dravya Guna Vigyan</i>
Kai. Ni.	<i>Kaiydeva Nighantu</i>	Ch. Chi.	<i>Charaka Samhita Chikitsa Sthana</i>
Ch. Su.	<i>Charaka Samhita Sutra Sthana</i>	Sha. Ni.	<i>Shaligrama Nighantu</i>
Dh. Ni.	<i>Dhanavantari Nighantu</i>	Ar. Pr.	<i>Arka Prakasha</i>
Su. Su.	<i>Susruta Samhita Sutra Sthana</i>	Sho. Ni.	<i>Sodhala Nighantu Bhushanam</i>
Ma. Ni.	<i>Madanpal Nighantu</i>		

CONCLUSION:

However, there are little studies has been carried out for the evaluation and validation particularly on the parameters of *Ayurveda* and Modern Science. Under the oriental studies it would be a great scope to search out lesser known medicinal plants utilizes folk medicine and having scientific basis and ultimately isolation, characterization and development of newer and lead phyto-medicinal components. Indigenous System of Medicine particularly *Ayurveda* and Folk

Medicine is considered as a major healthcare provider around the globe particularly in rural and remote areas. A large section of people depends on such medicine for their primary healthcare mainly in underdeveloped or developing countries. *Ayurveda* has a very rich history of their effectiveness; modern research also acknowledged the importance of such medicine. Folk Medicine or medicinal plants are also considered as a vital source of new drug. Mainstreaming of such medicine is important for the people. Several steps have been taken in India to promote such medicine and to integrate them into clinical practice. Evidence based incorporation of *Ayurveda* and Folk Medicine in clinical practice will help to provide quality healthcare to all.

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